

Multi-Objective Particle Swarm Optimization-Based Data Compression Algorithm for Public Datasets in Smart Grid Applications

*S.Karthika and Dr.P.Rathika

Assistant Professor, ECE Department, V V College of Engineering, Tisaiyanvilai, India

Email id: ns.karthika@yahoo.com

Professor, ECE Department, PSN College of Engineering and Technology, India

Email id: dr_p_rathika@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

In smart grid applications, a large amount of data is generated. This data is produced by intelligent devices, smart monitors, and measurement equipment, leading to substantial challenges in storage, computing, and transmission. Consequently, managing this vast amount of data contributes to the smart grid system becoming significantly more complex. To address these challenges, a data compression strategy is essential for enhancing the reliability and storage efficiency of the smart grid system when dealing with large amount of data. In response to this need, this paper proposes a novel data compression method specifically designed for smart grid data. The proposed approach leverages a unique combination of wavelet transform (WT) and multi-objective particle swarm optimization (MO-PSO) to achieve efficient data reduction. To validate the effectiveness of this technique, DRED (Dutch Residential Energy Datasets) datasets are utilized. The evaluation results demonstrate that the MO-PSO-based data compression algorithm outperforms traditional computation methods, offering superior performance in data compression for smart grid applications.

Index Terms-Particle Swarm Optimization, Wavelet Transform, Public Datasets, Smart Grid, Data Compression.

1. INTRODUCTION

Smart grid systems are crucial for modernizing power distribution, but they face significant challenges, particularly in managing the vast amount of data generated by monitoring and measuring devices. Effective data management is essential for storing, transmitting, processing,

and analyzing this data, which is critical for enhancing grid reliability, optimizing resource allocation, and integrating renewable energy sources. One of the primary issues is the substantial burden placed on infrastructure due to high-precision monitoring devices and the resulting data length, leading to high storage costs and complex data transmission challenges.

Data compression emerges as a vital solution to these challenges by reducing data length while preserving critical information. This approach decreases storage requirements, facilitates faster data transmission, and enhances the efficiency of data processing and analytics, thus ensuring quicker insights and reduced latency in control systems. Moreover, embedding data compression algorithms directly into monitoring devices for real-time applications can alleviate data congestion by compressing data before transmission. This not only reduces energy consumption for data handling but also supports the development of environmentally responsible smart grid systems. Consequently, this paper proposes a methodology for effectively compressing large datasets within smart grid systems to improve overall performance and efficiency.

In recent years, research in data compression for power system applications, particularly within the smart grid context, has gained considerable attention. In general, compression techniques can be broadly categorized into two main types: lossless compression and lossy compression [1]-[3]. The lossless-based data compression algorithms suffer from low compression ratio and high sampling rate. On the contrary, in the lossy-based data compression algorithms higher compression ratio can be reached. In addition to that, Lossy compression results in a significantly reduced sampling rate compared to lossless compression [4]. Therefore, the researchers focused towards lossy compression algorithms. Lossy compression algorithms for smart grid applications have been developed such as Cosine Transform (CT), Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), Wavelet Transform (WT), Principal Component Analysis, and Compressed Sensing Theory. [5]–[10].

In addition, the basic components of the signals are devised by cosine and sine functions such as CT and Fourier Transform (FT). They offer strong localization in the frequency domain. Moreover, these transformations are powerful tools for analyzing periodic and stationary signals, they may not be sufficient for signals with non-periodic, transient components, and power frequency changes. Panda et al. [5] have suggested the data compression using Slantlet transform

(SLT). In order to accomplish both time-localization and smoothness qualities, the Slantlet transform has been devised using the discrete time's length and moment. Yet, the compression ratio (CR) and information retention percentage are insufficient to detect the signals.

Wavelet Transform (WT) based Multi-Resolution Analysis (MRA) has been proposed as a compression technique by Ning et al. [11]. The Daubechies filters are essential components in the wavelet transform, serving as the "mother wavelets" that enable the decomposition of signals into different frequency bands with excellent time-frequency localization. They have proven to be valuable tools in signal and image processing tasks, particularly when analyzing and representing signals with varying frequency content. The properties of WT are directly related to the selection of a threshold that enables the regular signal element to be effectively approximated after thresholding [6]. But, selecting an optimal threshold value is the most important step in power system data compression. Hence an optimization algorithm is necessary to find the optimal threshold value. Similarly, Tcheou et al. [12] highlighted the advantages of wavelet-based compression in handling large-scale data from smart meters, emphasizing the balance between compression efficiency and data accuracy. However, manually determining the optimal threshold value is challenging due to the intricate balance required between CR, MSE, and SNR, highlighting the need for an automated approach to navigate this complexity effectively. This literature review underscores the effectiveness of data compression algorithms, especially those based on the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT), which heavily rely on selecting appropriate threshold values. These thresholds significantly impact critical parameters such as CR, MSE, and SNR

To automate the determination of the optimal threshold value in a DWT-based compression algorithm, an evolutionary-based algorithm is necessary. While single-objective optimization algorithms have been initially employed, they often fail to identify the optimal solution for data compression applications. This is supported by the findings of Hashemipour et al. [13], who noted that single-objective optimization techniques could not satisfactorily balance the trade-offs between CR, MSE, and SNR. Additionally, Diaz-Manriquez et al. [14] explored the limitations of single-objective methods and suggested that multi-objective optimization could provide better solutions by considering multiple performance metrics simultaneously. This indicates a critical research gap, emphasizing the need to explore alternative approaches that can handle the multi-objective nature of data compression problems. Unlike single-objective optimization, which

focuses solely on optimizing a single criterion, multi-objective optimization considers multiple objectives simultaneously, such as SNR, MSE, and CR.

In addition, Campos et al. [15] conducted a comparative study of different optimization techniques and concluded that multi-objective approaches could significantly enhance the performance of data compression algorithms by providing a balanced trade-off among multiple criteria. Therefore, this work aims to solve the data compression problem using a multi-objective optimization algorithm tailored for smart grid applications, addressing the complexity and improving the efficiency of data management in modern power systems.

Hence, the proposed methodology leverages a Multi-Objective Particle Swarm Optimization (MO-PSO) algorithm to address the intricate balance among multiple objectives in the data compression process. The MO-PSO algorithm is particularly suited for this task due to its capability to explore and exploit the search space effectively, handling multiple conflicting objectives simultaneously. By employing MO-PSO, this research seeks to optimize the trade-offs between compression ratio, mean square error, and signal-to-noise ratio, ensuring a comprehensive and balanced approach to data compression in smart grid systems. The MO-PSO algorithm's adaptive nature allows it to find optimal solutions more efficiently than traditional algorithms. Consequently, this approach not only enhances the data management capabilities of smart grid systems but also contributes to their overall performance, reliability, and efficiency.

II. PROPOSED MO-PSO ALGORITHM

Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) is a population-based optimization technique that has attracted considerable interest recently due to its effectiveness in solving diverse and complex optimization challenges. Drawing inspiration from the collective behavior of animals like fish and birds, PSO involves particles (individuals) working together to discover optimal solutions. The method relies on a combination of random exploration and systematic exploitation. Initially, the PSO algorithm sets up a group of particles, each representing a possible solution in the problem's search space. These particles navigate the search space by updating their positions and velocities based on their own experiences and the shared knowledge of the swarm. The algorithm continually

assesses the fitness of each particle relative to the objective function to gauge the quality of their solutions.

The Multi-Objective Particle Swarm Optimization (MO-PSO) algorithm for data compression in smart grid systems aims to simultaneously minimize mean square error (MSE), maximize signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), and minimize compression ratio (CR). The objective function is represented as a vector $[f_1(x), f_2(x), f_3(x)]$, where $f_1(x)$ minimizes MSE, $f_2(x)$ maximizes SNR, and $f_3(x)$ minimizes CR. The decision variables are the compression thresholds, denoted as $x_i = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$, where n is the number of decision variables, influencing the compression outcome by selectively retaining or discarding information. The constraints ensure that the decision variables stay within predefined bounds ($x_{min} \leq x_i \leq x_{max}$) and maintain acceptable compression quality ($CR_n < CR_t, SNR_n > SNR_t, MSE_n < MSE_t$). Here, $CR_n, SNR_n,$ and MSE_n represent the newly generated metrics from the PSO algorithm, while $CR_t, SNR_t,$ and MSE_t are the target values that guide the optimization process. These constraints ensure that the newly generated metrics do not exceed their respective target values, thus guiding the algorithm towards achieving efficient compression while preserving data quality. By optimizing these parameters, the MO-PSO algorithm aims to find optimal threshold values that balance MSE, SNR, and CR, leading to effective data compression in smart grid systems.

The suggested algorithmic program (Fig.1) is explained as follows. The algorithm starts with input data from a smart grid. The input signals in the smart grid dataset are decomposed via the DWT-based MRA. By integrating the MO-PSO algorithm into a DWT-based compression algorithm, the selection of the optimal threshold value becomes automated.

Initially, the MO-PSO algorithm begins with the initialization phase, where a population of particles is created with random positions and velocities. Each particle's fitness is evaluated based on the multiple objective functions that define the optimization problem. Subsequently, non-dominated solutions within the population are identified, and these solutions are stored in an external repository known as the Pareto archive. These non-dominated solutions represent the trade-off between conflicting objectives and serve as benchmarks for the optimization process.

As the optimization progresses, the particles velocities and positions are updated. Following the update, the objective function of the particles based on their new positions is evaluated. The personal best positions for each particle and the global best positions for the swarm are updated accordingly to track the best solutions found so far.

Fig.1 MO-PSO Algorithm

Incorporating an elitist mutation operation introduces diversity into the population, helping to explore the search space more effectively. This mutation operator selects a subset of particles from the current population and applies a perturbation to their positions. The mutated particles are then evaluated, and if they are non-dominated or contribute to improving the diversity in the population, they replace the original particles. This mutation operation helps in escaping local optima and maintaining a diverse set of solutions in the Pareto archive.

Throughout the optimization process, the external repository of non-dominated solutions is updated by combining the current population with the Pareto archive. Dominated solutions are removed from the combined set, and the size of the repository is controlled to prevent it from growing excessively. The optimization procedure continues iteratively until a termination criterion is met, such as reaching a maximum number of iterations. Finally, the Pareto solutions can be retrieved from the external repository.

The optimal threshold value is obtained from the Pareto solutions using a ranking method applied to the DWT coefficients. This algorithm enabling selective retention or elimination based on the threshold value, thereby shortening the initial signal length. The reconstructed signal is synthesized using the retained approximation coefficients and detail coefficients, thus storing the original signal at the receiving end.

Finally, the effectiveness of the compression algorithm is assessed using performance metrics such as CR, MSE, and SNR.

A. *Compression Ratio (CR)*

In order to assess the goodness of compression, the compression ratio (*CR*) is computed by finding the ratio of the original data length to the compressed data length. It is given by

$$CR = \frac{\text{Original Data Length}}{\text{Compressed Data Length}} \quad (1)$$

B. Mean Square Error (MSE)

The MSE represents the cumulative square error between the reconstructed signal and the original signal.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum ((f(u, v) - f'(u, v))^2) \quad (2)$$

where n is the length of the signal, $f(u, v)$ is the original signal & $f'(u, v)$ is the reconstructed signal.

C. Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)

The strength of a desired signal in relation to background noise is measured by the SNR. The SNR is defined as

$$SNR = 10 * \log_{10} \left(\frac{(f(u, v))^2}{(f(u, v) - f'(u, v))^2} \right) \quad (3)$$

where $f(u, v)$ is the original signal & $f'(u, v)$ is the reconstructed signal.

These metrics provide quantifiable measures of the trade-off between CR, MSE and SNR, allowing for an evaluation of the algorithm's performance in compressing smart grid data while maintaining data integrity and quality.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

MATLAB is used to implement the proposed data compression algorithm. In addition, this research utilizes dataset obtained from the DRED (<https://st.ewi.tudelft.nl/~akshay/dred/>) smart grid dataset to assess the effectiveness of data compression techniques. The Dataset incorporates electricity monitoring data, encompassing both aggregated energy usage and appliance-level energy consumption.

Fig. 2 DWT-based data compression results for Dataset C

Fig.2 shows DWT-based data compression results for DRED Dataset. For example, the washing machine dataset has 297 samples of the original signal compressed with a CR of 3.0938. In order to compress the signal at CR=3.0938, the 96 detail coefficients are retained, and 201 lower coefficients are set to zero. The reconstructed signal matches the original signal with an MSE of 0.1065 and SNR of 70.8652.

Table 1 DWT-based data compression results for DRED Dataset

Types of Signals	Original Signal Length	Discrete Wavelet Transform Based Data Compression				
		T (Threshold)	CR (Compression Ratio)	MSE (Mean Square Error)	SNR in db (Signal to Noise Ratio)	Compressed Signal Length
Average Power(Washing Machine)	297	1.4496	3.0938	0.1065	70.8652	96
Average Power(Aggregate Data)	223	0.0707	1.9391	0.00032	70.7271	115

Also, Table 1 gives details about the length of the original signal, Threshold (T), CR, MSE, SNR and length of the compressed signal obtained from DWT-based data compression.

For the case of WT, the above simulations are executed by directly applying universal thresholds for neglecting certain wavelet coefficients. But, the performance of data compression varies for different threshold values. Hence, to find the optimum threshold value, an optimization algorithm is needed.

Hence, selection of the optimum threshold is an essential process for data compression algorithm. Next, the MO-PSO algorithm applied to select the appropriate threshold value T. The important parameters of the MO-PSO are: swarm size (N), inertia weight (ω), personal learning factor ($c1$), global learning factor ($c2$), and maximum iteration (kmax). These values are crucial for implementing the optimal threshold.

The Specific parameter settings are listed in Table 2. Following the selection of the parameter values, simulations for DRED data sets were executed.

Table 2 Parameter Settings of multi-objective Particle Swarm Optimization

Parameter	Value
No. of Particles	20
inertia weight, ω	0.9-0.1
global learning factor ($c1$)	0.5
global learning factor ($c2$)	0.5
Maximum Iteration	150

The MO-PSO algorithm, integrated with DWT-based data compression, is implemented for smart grid applications. In the following sections, the results are presented and discussed. The results obtained from the MO-PSO algorithm, in conjunction with general WT-based data compression algorithms, are presented in Table 3.

The MO-PSO algorithm is implemented with target values for CR, MSE and SNR, which were generated from the WT-based data compression algorithm. These performance metrics served as multiple objectives for the MO-PSO algorithm, which aimed to find the optimal threshold value while considering compression quality constraint.

Table 3 Optimal threshold obtained from MO-PSO algorithm for DRED Dataset

Types of Signals	Original Signal Length	Multiple Objectives			Threshold value (T) achieved from MO-PSO algorithm
		CR_t	MSE_t	SNR_t	
Average Power (Washing Machine)	297	3.0938	0.1065	70.8652	0.5266
Average Power (Aggregate Data)	223	1.9391	0.00032	70.7271	0.0823

Table 3 shows the results obtained from the MO-PSO algorithm. CR_t represents the target CR assigned to the MO-PSO algorithm, indicating the desired compression level to be achieved. Similarly, SNR_t and MSE_t denote the target SNR and MSE, respectively, guiding the optimization process towards preserving signal quality and minimizing distortion. For instance, DRED dataset, which includes washing machine and aggregate data signals, the algorithm yielded optimal threshold values of 0.5266 and 0.0823, respectively.

The next step is to apply this optimal value to WT-based data compression. This process entails decomposing the data into a set of coefficients using the WT, where certain coefficients are set to zero based on the threshold value determined by the MO-PSO algorithm. Consequently, this thresholding process eliminates the unwanted coefficients, effectively reducing the initial signal length. The simulation results are shown in Table 4 (a).

Table 4 (a) MO-PSO based data compression results for DRED Dataset

Types of Signals	Original Signal Length	Threshold value T achieved from MO-PSO algorithm	CR_n	MSE_n	SNR_n in dB	Compressed Signal Length
Average Power (Washing Machine)	297	0.5266	2.3023	0.0173	78.7655	129
Average Power (Aggregate Data)	223	0.0823	1.9735	3.131e-04	70.4663	113

Table 4 (b) Performance comparison of data compression algorithms

DATASETS	Typed of Signals	Original Signal Length	T (Threshold)	CR (Compression Ratio)	MSE (Mean Square Error)	SNR in dB (Signal-to-noise Ratio)	Compressed Signal Length
Washing Machine)	WT	297	1.4496	3.0938	0.1065	70.8652	96
	MO-PSO	297	0.5266	2.3023	0.0173	78.7655	129

From Table 4 (a), it is observed that the compression process resulted in reduced signal length while improving signal quality, as indicated by decreased MSE values and increased SNR. Moreover, the results obtained by the MO-PSO algorithm are compared with those obtained by the WT based data compression algorithm. Compared to the WT-based data compression without optimization algorithm, the WT-based data compression with the MO-PSO algorithm performs better.

Also, For examining the washing machine’s voltage signal with 297 samples, with WT-based data compression, a CR of 3.0938 was achieved, whereas, Table 4 (b) presents a CR of 2.3023 with the MO-PSO algorithm. Despite the lower CR, the MSE decreased from 0.1065 to 0.0173, and the SNR increased from 70.8652 to 78.7655, reflecting notable improvements in signal fidelity and quality.

Fig. 3 MO-PSO-based data compression results for DRED Dataset

Fig. 3 shows MO-PSO-based data compression results for DRED Datasets. Overall, these results demonstrate the effectiveness of the MO-PSO-based data compression approach in reducing signal length while preserving signal quality across various datasets.

IV. CONCLUSION

The current work suggests an efficient Multi Objective PSO-based threshold-based data compression algorithm for smart grid systems. The proposed approach will assist the communications system in handling the task of transmitting large amount of data in smart grid systems. The performance evaluation of the MO-PSO algorithm is validated based on various objective functions, which include minimization of CR, minimization of MSE, and maximization of SNR. Moreover, the results obtained by the MO-PSO algorithm are compared with the WT-based data compression algorithm. Compared to the WT-based data compression algorithm, the WT-based data compression with the MO-PSO algorithm performs better.

REFERENCES

1. Lulu Wen, Kaile Zhou, Shanlin Yang and Lanlan Lia (2018) “Compression of smart meter big data: A survey”, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol.91, pp.59-69.
2. Douglas L.S. Mendes , Ricardo A.L. Rabelo , Artur F.S. Veloso , Joel J.P.C. Rodrigues and Jose V. dos Reis Junior (2020) ” An adaptive data compression mechanism for smart meters considering a demand side management scenario”, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 255 pp.1-11.
3. Shouxiang Wang, Haiwen Chen, Lei Wu, Jianfeng Wang (2020)” A novel smart meter data compression method via stacked convolutional sparse auto-encoder”, *Electrical Power and Energy Systems*,vol.118, pp. 1-11.
4. Kunqi Jiaa, Ge Guo, Jucheng Xiao, Huan Zhou, Zhihua Wang, Guangyu He (2019)” Data compression approach for the home energy management system”, *Applied Energy*, vol. 247,pp. 643–656.
5. G. Panda, P. K. Dash, A. K. Pradhan, and S. K. Meher (2002) ” Data Compression of Power Quality Events Using the Slantlet Transform”, *IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON POWER DELIVERY*, VOL. 17, NO. 2, pp.662-667.
6. Dileep G (2020)” A survey on smart grid technologies and applications”, *Renewable Energy*, vol.146, pp.2589-2625.
7. Gyul Lee, and Yong-June Shin (2017)” Multiscale PMU Data Compression Based on Wide-Area Event Detection”, *IEEE International Conference on Smart Grid Communications*, pp.437-442.
8. F. Pabón and E. Inga (2015)” State of Art, Meter Data Management System Using Compressed Sensing for AMI Based on Wavelet”, *IEEE LATIN AMERICA TRANSACTIONS*, VOL. 13, NO. 12,pp.3774-3780, DECEMBER.
9. Yi Sun, Can Cui and Jun Lu, Qi Wang (2016)” Data compression and reconstruction of smart grid customers based on compressed sensing theory”, *Electrical Power and Energy Systems*, vol. 83,pp. 21–25.
10. Fang Zhang, , IEEE, Lin Cheng, Xiong Li, Yuanzhang Sun, IEEE, Wenzhong Gao and Weixing Zhao (2018)” Application of a Real-Time Data Compression and Adapted Protocol Technique for WAMS”, *IEEE Transactions On Power Systems*, vol.78, pp-1-10.
11. Jiaxin Ning, Jianhui Wang, Wenzhong Gao and Cong Liu (2011) “A Wavelet-Based Data Compression Technique for Smart Grid” *IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON SMART GRID*, vol. 2, pp. 212-218.
12. Tcheou, MP, Lovisolio, L, Ribeiro, MV, Da Silva, EA, Rodrigues, MA, Romano, JM & Diniz, PS 2013, ‘The compression of electric signal waveforms for smart grids: State of the art and future trends’, *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp.291-302.

13. Hashemipour, N, Aghaei, J, Salimi, L, Granado, P, Shafie-khah, M & Catalao, JP 2021, 'Optimal Singular Value Decomposition Based Big Data Compression Approach in Smart Grids' IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications, vol. 57, no.4, pp. 3296 – 3305.
14. Diaz-Manriquez, A, Toscano, G, Barron-Zambrano, JH & Tello-Leal, E 2016, 'R2-Based Multi/Many-Objective Particle Swarm Optimization', Computational Intelligence and Neuroscience, vol. 2016, article no. 1898527, pp. 1-10.
15. Campos, Jr, A, Pozo, AT & Duarte Jr, EP 2019, 'Parallel Multi-Swarm PSO Strategies for Solving Many Objective Optimization Problems', Journal of Parallel and Distributed Computing, vol. 126, pp. 13-33